

FEATURES OF THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE BANKING SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The scientific thesis examines some aspects of the use digital technologies in the banking system of the Uzbekistan based on the study of advanced experience of developed countries, and examines the scientific and theoretical views of foreign economists on banking innovations. Consequently, scientific conclusions, proposals and recommendations on the introduction and development of innovations in banking system of Uzbekistan were formed.

Key words: commercial banks, innovations, financial technologies, mobile applications, remote banking services, digital technologies.

In order to ensure the financial stability of banks and protect the interests of depositors and creditors, it is necessary to comply with prudential standards set by the Central Bank, and one of these prudential standards is the liquidity ratio, which determines the need to establish a reliable liquidity system in banks¹.

Devaluation reserves are included in the fixed capital of commercial banks and are not a relatively stable source of financing for banking activities. As Chris Barltrop, an expert with the World Bank for Reconstruction and Development, puts it: “Bank capital is a reliable and relatively expensive form of financing banking activities”². Therefore, it is expedient to include the amount formed on the balance sheet of a commercial bank at the expense of devaluation reserves in the additional capital structure.

Theoretical, methodological and practical issues of innovations in banking system were studied in the scientific works of foreign scientists, economists such as E. Gill, T. Koch, E. Reed, X. Grüning, E. Dollan, L. Roger, A. Simanovsky, O. Lavrushin, V. Usoskin, G. Panova, J. Sinki, R. Kotter, W. Soto, Moiseev, E. Zhukova, G. Beloglazova, N. Valentseva, A. Gavrilenko, V. Kolesnikov, G. Korobova, L. Batrakova, A. Litvinova, O. Ovchinnikova, G. Panova, V. Rodionova, I. Rykov, G. Tosunyan and others³.

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Banks and Banking” (No. ZRU-580 of 05.11.2019)

² Diana McNaughton, Chris Barltrop. Banking institutions in developing countries. Washington, DC, IDE, 1993., p. 21.

³ Rutgajzer V. M. and Buditsky A. E. Estimation of the market value of a commercial bank URL: <https://www.livelib.ru/author/208447/latest-v-m-rutgajzer-a-e-buditskij>

In today's world, leading banks strive to endlessly improve the quality of their banking services while reducing the cost of their maintenance. The range of banking and financial services is expanding every year, new types of products and services are constantly appearing on the market. This factor serves to intensify competition between banks for each client.

Improving the system of cashless payments in the banking system directly depends on the development of new banking products. Banking innovations are a powerful tool for the socio-economic development of society. Under the influence of many economic and social factors, banking products and services are evolving. The Central Bank of Uzbekistan and commercial banks are expanding cashless payment systems and Internet banking, mobile banking, and SMS banking are becoming more accessible to customers.

Table 1

Information about issued banking cards, POS-terminals, ATM's and Self-Service Kiosks as of 1 March 2025, also transactions carried out through POS-terminals in January-February of 2025⁴

No	Commercial banks	Number of bank cards issued into circulation	Number of installed POS-terminals	Number of installed ATMs and Self-Service Kiosks	The amount of transactions carried out through POS-terminals in January-February 2025 <i>(in mln. sum)</i>
1	National bank	4 000 425	39 123	875	3 781 379
2	Uzbek Industrial and Construction Bank	2 768 701	31 424	680	2 286 806
3	Agrobank	5 504 211	38 779	2 166	2 714 404
4	People's Bank	10 639 555	46 378	3 064	1 931 764
5	Hamkorbank	3 128 105	37 920	677	2 640 873
6	Asaka bank	1 568 344	14 604	259	2 139 204
7	Ipak Yuli bank	3 162 169	22 185	959	2 061 528
8	Aloqabank	1 988 545	13 980	244	7 654 053
9	Ipoteka-bank	4 816 727	34 492	785	4 306 017
10	Octobank	4 617 509	860	54	3 747 130
11	TBC bank	5 886 006	27	0	4 404 925
12	Anor bank	2 845 793	1 386	0	374 497
	Total	62 033 647	427 104	32 265	62 885 593

⁴<https://cbu.uz/ru/statistics/paysistem/2241846/>

As shown in the table above, People's Bank prevails in terms of the number of issued plastic cards and installed payment terminals. As of March 1, 2025, 36 banks operate in Uzbekistan. Thus, 12 commercial banks account for more than 81.2% of the issued plastic cards, more than 65.8% in terms of the number of installed payment terminals, more than 30.3% in terms of the number of installed ATMs and information kiosks, and more than 60.5% in terms of receipts through payment terminals indicated in the table.

In order to ensure the financial stability of banks and protect the interests of depositors and creditors, it is necessary to comply with prudential standards set by the Central Bank, and one of these prudential standards is the liquidity ratio, which determines the need to establish a reliable liquidity system in banks⁵.

One of the main risks for banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to improve the quality of credit portfolio and risk management, pursue a moderate growth of lending, pursue a balanced macroeconomic policy, ensure technological stability of the banking system through the implementation of technological solutions for assessing financial risks liquidity risks will need to be identified and managed early⁶.

It is known from international banking practice that the primary means of ensuring the solvency and liquidity of commercial banks is to strengthen their capital base. In turn, the strengthening of the capital base of commercial banks will be achieved by improving the system of effective capital management. At present, there are a number of issues that need to be addressed to ensure the stability of the capital of commercial banks of the country. In particular, the problem of effective management of the authorized capital of commercial banks and the efficiency of the use of bank assets.

One of the main risks for banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to improve the quality of credit portfolio and risk management, pursue a moderate growth of lending, pursue a balanced macroeconomic policy, ensure technological stability of the banking system through the implementation of technological solutions for assessing financial risks liquidity risks will need to be identified and managed early ⁷.

The actualization of these factors largely determines the logic of the study of the mechanism of cashless payments in the transition to a digital economy. At the same time, not only the development of the theoretical provisions of this problem is of great importance, but also their practical application, including in

⁵ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Banks and Banking" (No. ZRU-580 of 05.11.2019)

⁶ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5992 "On the strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025" January 12, 2020.

⁷ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5992 "On the strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025" January 12, 2020.

the framework of the development and implementation of an effective and integrated payment system.

According to our local scientist R. Shomurodov, an expert on monetary policy: The results of a study of the financial and banking system of developed and developing countries show that the capitalization of commercial banks directly affects the development and stability of the country's economy. Bank loans also support the development of small and medium-sized businesses, private entrepreneurship and stimulate the development of infrastructure for an innovative and digital economy in the country⁸.

The globalization of all processes affects the emergence of new models and digital technologies. Therefore, today the banking industry is rapidly changing under the influence of a number of global challenges: changing consumer preferences of customers; the emergence of new technologies and the pace of implementation of existing ones; decrease in the marginality of the global banking sector and increased regulatory requirements; competition from FinTech companies.

Thus, as of January 1, 2025, of the total assets of the National Bank of Uzbekistan amount to 135.090 billion soums. In terms of loans, of the National Bank of Uzbekistan ranks first with 108.014 billion soums. In turn, the capitalization of the National Bank is 18.860 billion soums, and the National Bank of Uzbekistan Bank leads in deposits with 36,839 billion soums⁹.

The lack of issue income in the capital of commercial banks of the country indicates that the secondary market of securities issued by commercial banks is underdeveloped and is not considered as an object of regular trading. However, in the capital of commercial banks in many foreign countries, the amount of issue income occupies a significant share. For example, it is second only to the government in terms of the volume of securities issued by commercial banks in the United States, the United Kingdom and Japan, and their participation in trading in financial markets. Given that one of the most convenient and profitable areas in the process of further deepening the liberalization of the economy is to increase the amount of resources attracted by commercial banks through issuance of shares and certificates of deposit, then regular participation of commercial banks in securities market development its role in making it even more pronounced.

Improving the system of cashless payments in the banking system directly depends on the development of new banking products. Banking innovations are a powerful tool for the socio-economic development of society. Under the influence of many economic and social factors, banking products and services

⁸ Shomurodov R. T. et al. Issues of increasing the capitalization of commercial banks in the context of innovation // Young scientist. – 2021. – N. 25. - P. 237-243. URL: <https://moluch.ru/authors/131302/>

⁹ <https://cbu.uz/ru/statistics/bankstats/2122860/>

are evolving. The Central Bank of Uzbekistan and commercial banks are expanding cashless payment systems and Internet banking, mobile banking, and SMS banking are becoming more accessible to customers.

1. In addition, the significant changes that have occurred over the past decades in the banking system of Uzbekistan and other countries, namely those related to the emergence of new types of services and technologies of the banking sector, actualize the problem of increasing the competitiveness and efficiency of providing banking services.

2. However, despite a significant number of studies devoted to theoretical, methodological and applied problems that arise in the process of developing cashless payments, in the context of the introduction of information and innovative technologies in the banking system, in our opinion, the theoretical and methodological support of this process has not been fully formed.

3. Innovations have become a characteristic feature of modern development in all spheres of the economy, including banking. In a highly competitive environment, it is important to find a way to retain existing customers and attract new ones, this is doubly difficult.

4. Developed countries have many years of experience in introducing, developing and improving the system of cashless payments based on innovation and digital technology. In addition, an analysis of the best practices of developed countries shows that the system of cashless payments has been improved under the influence of innovative ideas and technologies.

5. For large-scale innovations, a fundamentally new level of interaction between big business, the state, science and technology entrepreneurs is needed. In fact, large companies and basic research are the sources of most global innovation.

6. Improving the system of cashless payments in the banking system directly depends on the development of new banking products. Banking innovations are a powerful tool for the socio-economic development of society. Under the influence of many factors, the evolution of banking products and services is taking place.

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9. Prepared by the author based on information from the bank’s website – www.bank.uz

